

WAYS TO INCREASE THERMAL CHARACTERISTICS IN BUILDING CONSTRUCTION

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Annotation: The article discusses the problems of increasing the thermal efficiency of building buildings and structures. The advantages and disadvantages of various methods for improving the thermal protection characteristics of building envelopes through the use of modern effective technologies are discussed.

Key words: structures, buildings, external enclosing structures, external walls, thermal insulation materials, disadvantages, advantages.

Introduction. The limited availability of energy resources, their constant rise in price, the negative impact on the environment associated with energy production are factors that have influenced the fact that one of the main priority areas of economic development of the Republic of Uzbekistan is energy saving [1, 3]. Currently, Uzbek construction standards are being adjusted in accordance with global and European standardization standards. This has led to the fact that the existing stock of residential and public buildings is ineffective in terms of thermal characteristics. Therefore, improving energy-saving activities in the design and operation of a residential complex, increasing the thermal efficiency of the building envelope, including walls, coverings and windows, is an urgent task [2, 4, 5].

The problem of improving energy saving in construction buildings was dealt with by S. Yu. Pleshkov, A. Kuchkarov, K. B. Usmanov, A. L. Naumov, D. V. Kapko and others. Thus, in the works of E.I. Vakunina developed a number of measures aimed at improving energy-saving activities during the operation of a housing complex. S. Yu. Pleshkov and L. G. Pastukhova propose a solution to the

problem of sealing a building in energy-efficient construction due to high-quality thermal insulation and the problem of energy saving in energy-efficient construction through the use of high-quality double-glazed windows and design solutions in the production and installation of double-glazed windows, premises. V. M. Manankov developed a design for additional thermal insulation of external walls using a material such as penofol. A.L. Naumov and D.V. Kapko developed a methodology for determining the energy consumption of engineering systems of buildings being commissioned and assigning an energy efficiency class to these buildings. They substantiated the importance of materials for improving the energy efficiency of buildings.

Thus, today there are many methods, methods and proposals that solve the problem of energy saving in construction buildings [6, 9]. At the same time, a problem arises that not all the needs of a modern user can be met by existing energy saving methods [7, 8].

The most effective measure to reduce thermal energy losses in a residential building is to improve the thermal protection characteristics of enclosing structures. Such a reduction is achieved by implementing the following measures:

- insulation of external walls;
- replacing windows with more modern ones;
- roof insulation.

To reduce heat losses through external enclosing structures, various heat-insulating materials are used, which are distinguished by the type of raw material, structure, form of release, density, thermal conductivity, rigidity, fire and moisture resistance, and method of application [10].

According to the type of raw materials from which thermal insulation materials are made, they are divided into organic (wood fiber boards, peat slabs, reeds, ecowool, cork), inorganic (mineral wool, glass wool, foam concrete and aerated concrete, polystyrene foam, expanded polystyrene), and composite thermal insulation materials contain organic and inorganic fillers. Insulation of external

building envelopes with mineral wool and polystyrene foam is mainly carried out using two technologies:

- a) technology of hinged “ventilated” facade;
- b) “wet” facade technology.

The technology of a suspended “ventilated” facade is also called dry wall insulation. The technology is that a sheathing made of wooden beams, boards or a galvanized metal profile is attached to the wall, into which insulation is placed. A moisture-proof membrane is attached to the sheathing on top of the insulation, and a counter-lattice is attached to the membrane, to which decorative sheathing, usually siding, is attached. By using a counter-lattice, a gap is formed between the outer skin and the moisture-proof membrane in which air circulates, thereby ventilating this space and removing moisture from it. Hence the name “ventilated facade” [6].

Advantages of hinged ventilated facades:

- the presence of a natural ventilation system that facilitates the removal of excess moisture;
- the declared maximum service life of the structure is about 50 years;
- good soundproofing qualities;
- the installation of a ventilated facade eliminates the need for facing work;
- efficiency during routine repairs;
- no restrictions on weather conditions during installation and repair work;

Disadvantages of hinged ventilated facades:

- higher cost of installation and ongoing repairs compared to “wet” facades;
- the need for more careful analysis and calculation when constructing facades on buildings with large numbers of floors;
- high complexity of installation, the need for highly qualified and extensive experience of workers;
- high cost of materials, the need to use, in addition to direct thermal insulation, special windproof and waterproof coatings.

The principle of the “wet” facade technology or, in other words, “insulation under plaster” is that a heat-insulating material is attached to the wall surface using a special adhesive composition and mounting dowels, on the surface of which a layer reinforced using a mesh is created and a plaster layer is applied on top . solution [5, 7].

The advantages of the wet method include the low cost and light weight of the system, which allows it to be used on almost all types of buildings without strengthening the foundation or strengthening load-bearing structures. The declared service life is up to 25 years. The system has good soundproofing qualities.

Disadvantages of the technology include seasonality. This is due to high requirements during installation work, such as compliance with the temperature regime (from 5°C to 30°C), the absence of high humidity, strong wind, and bright sunlight. High demands on a good combination of materials.

Currently, a new way of insulating buildings has emerged - painting walls with thin-film energy-saving paint. Energy-saving paint is an emulsion consisting of a connecting component and microscopic ceramic or glass hollow spheres with a diameter of 0.03 ÷ 0.1 mm.

Energy-saving paints have the properties of paints - they protect the surface from environmental influences - and the properties of thermal insulation - they reduce heat losses due to their porous structure.

The advantages of energy-saving paints include:

- low cost of paint production;
- good adhesion to any materials except polyethylene;
- mechanical strength;
- antifungal and anti-mold properties;
- moisture and vapor resistance of the coating;
- resistance to ultraviolet radiation;
- low cost of painting work;
- environmental and fire safety;

- low weight and, as a result, the absence of additional loads on the enclosing structures;
- high aesthetic appearance of painted enclosing structures.

The disadvantage of this technology for insulating facades is the relatively low thermal protection indicators. Windows also play an important role in improving thermal insulation characteristics.

Up to a third of the thermal energy spent on heating is lost through problematic windows. Traditionally, house windows were made from wood elements with glazing with one or two window frames. During the cold period, an additional second window frame was installed to single window frames. This practice was common for single-family houses. In multi-storey buildings and public buildings, double frames were installed permanently. Currently, traditional window design no longer meets the increasing level of thermal requirements.

To insulate the roof, you can use both foam plastic and mineral wool. The vapor permeability of polystyrene foam is practically zero. When using polystyrene foam as a thermal insulation material on the roof, regardless of its type, a greenhouse effect is created in the attic. This can lead to mold and mildew. Therefore, when choosing polystyrene foam as a thermal insulation material, special attention should be paid to roof and roof ventilation. Unlike polystyrene foam, penoizol allows you to fill almost all inaccessible places. Thus, most of the so-called cold bridges are eliminated, and the roof becomes warmer. The positive thing about using polystyrene foam (apart from high-quality insulation) is its low cost. It is advisable to use polystyrene foam in rooms where people are rarely present and in attics.

Mineral wool, as insulation for the roof of a house, is more expensive than polystyrene foam. The advantages of using mineral wool, firstly, are that it is vapor permeable (does not create a greenhouse effect and regulates the microclimate under the roof); secondly, it is environmentally friendly; and thirdly, it is universal - it can be used to insulate the roof of both residential and non-residential attics. Of all the varieties of mineral wool, the best option is the one that is applied using a compressor

- such insulation for a sloping roof, as well as penoizol, allows you to fill everything, even the most inaccessible places. As for other types of mineral wool, their efficiency is slightly lower - with equal success you can use both rolled roof insulation and its equivalent, made in the form of slabs.

Today, mineral insulation is used to insulate the roofs of private houses - polystyrene foam is used exclusively in extreme cases, when there is a huge budget deficit.

Conclusions. An analysis of the state of the problem of increasing the thermal efficiency of building buildings has shown that this problem is not fully covered by modern researchers and there is great potential for increasing the thermal efficiency of buildings by improving the heat-protective characteristics of enclosing structures.

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